

From Conflict to Reconstruction: Assessing Nepal's Transformation in Post-Maoist Insurgency

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Abstract

Conflict remains a pressing global issue that poses significant threats to global peace. Rooted in social and economic conditions such as caste, ethnicity, gender, class, religion, poverty, and hunger, conflict manifests in various forms including violence, battles, wars, and internal strife, causing mental distress and fear among affected populations. The pursuit of development, peace, and prosperity hinges on maintaining peaceful societal conditions.

In Nepal, numerous intersecting variables of conflict, such as caste, religion, ethnicity, gender, language, and regional disparities, contribute to its complex social landscape. The country's transition to a Federal Republic under the Interim Constitution of Nepal 2063 and ongoing state restructuring processes present substantial challenges to development efforts. Effectively addressing these differences is crucial to prevent potential resurgence of violent conflict in the future.

Despite the challenges posed by past conflict, Nepal has witnessed positive transformations that have significantly impacted the lives of its people. These changes underscore the importance of managing and resolving societal differences to foster sustainable development and lasting peace.

Keywords: Conflict, Constituent Assembly, Permanent peace, Federal republic, Inclusiveness.

Introduction

Conflict arises when there is disagreement in ideas and opposing goals or values among closely associated parties or groups. Individuals naturally differ in their thoughts, opinions, and ideologies, leading to such disagreements. Conflict, an inherent part of human existence, invariably catalyzes societal change, which can be either beneficial or detrimental (Adhikari & Pyakurel, 2013).

Nepal faces severe levels of partiality, mainly in various social institutions and zones groups and regions in the nation. In its culturally and ethnically diverse landscape, previous efforts towards democratization have predominantly benefited the elite, perpetuating exclusion and marginalization rather than fostering widespread participation. If left unaddressed, this inequality not only jeopardizes physical infrastructure but also impedes overall development. Addressing both manageable and challenging conflicts is crucial, alongside exploring strategies for conflict transformation and lasting peace. Nepal, known for its multi-ethnic and multicultural makeup, was documented in the 2011 census to encompass 126 social division and indigenous people, 123 linguistics variants, and 10 cultural communities (CBS, Census Report, 2011). Despite Hinduism predominating among 81% of the population, there is no dominant ethnic group, highlighting a landscape rich in minorities. The disparities between these groups and across various regions remain notably pronounced.

Poverty indicators are significantly elevated among Janajatis, indigenous peoples, and Dalits in Nepal compared to higher caste groups. Rural areas experience much lower average per capita income than urban areas, with a significant portion of these marginalized communities residing in rural settings. Moreover, the average household and individual consumption levels are notably deficient among socially excluded and marginalized groups. These economic disparities contribute significantly to societal tensions and conflicts (UNDP Report, 2006). Economic and social strategies for resolving conflicts include providing development aid, implementing economic reforms, ensuring fair distribution of resources, fostering social and economic development, initiating agricultural projects, boosting private sector investments, and eliminating all forms of inequalities and disparities while safeguarding minority rights. These measures were endorsed by the United Nations Socio-Economic Council (Shivakoti, 2070). Lessons from Sri Lanka's experience with significant social inequalities can be instructive in this regard. Nepal is a nation characterized by diverse castes, races, regions, religions, genders, and ethnicities, yet many of these groups experience significant social exclusion. This paper aims to explore primary and secondary information gathered from various sources regarding the causes and repercussions of this exclusion within society. The study emphasizes that the most effective solution to address issues like exclusion and inequality is to integrate these marginalized groups across all sectors in proportion to their population. This approach aims to foster a sense of national unity and equal identity among all citizens. Such inclusive practices are envisioned to pave the way for the creation of a cohesive New Nepal, free from disruptions, conflicts, controversies, and misunderstandings.

Nepal is characterized by its diversity with multiple ethnicities and cultures. The 2011 census revealed that Nepal is home to 125 distinct caste and ethnic groups, 123 languages, and 10 different religious communities (CBS 2012, 4). Hindus constitute 81.3% of the population. There is no single dominant ethnic group, with a variety of minorities present (Thapa and Sijapati 2004, 77). Ethnic and regional disparities have been notably pronounced, particularly during the 1990s, positioning Nepal among the most unequal countries in South Asia (Lawoti 2007, 10). Although Nepal's overall Human Development Index ranking has improved, this progress has largely been limited to urban areas such as the Kathmandu Valley (Einsiedel, Malone, and Pradan 2012). Historically, Nepal has seen minimal inter-ethnic or inter-group conflicts, with ethnic identities only recently gaining political importance (Sharma 1997, 472). The process of the managing the apt and appropriate condition of the ongoing politics and arranging all the required demands of the marginalized groups has naturally become one of the challenges for the nation. The demands and expectation of the people has become high and to meet the needs of the time has turned as the greatest challenge to all the political parties. Discussing about the challenges of the reconstruction of the nation after the Maoist insurgency, it has become as hard as Adhikari et al (2020) have claimed in keeping the ecology and the environment of the world and it is as complex as Adhikari et al (2022) have discussed about the global condition of the system of the government and it has turned out as beyond the control as Adhikari (2020) has analyzed about the existing condition of the world's deteriorating system of the environment and ecology due to the governments of the world and it

is because of the dominance of the foreign superpowers. However, it has to be carried out effectively for the reconstruction and transformation of the country for the entire change that has become essential for the Nepalese people.

Statement of Problem

Conflicts stem from the diversity among individuals, including differences in their thoughts, ideologies, needs, desires, and opinions. These differences are a perpetual force that can either drive change or lead to destruction. Conflict has been present since ancient times and has evolved alongside human development. It serves as a persistent catalyst for violence within societies or nations, often resulting in detrimental consequences. The peaceful state of society is crucial for its development, peace, and prosperity. In Nepal, various factors of conflict intersect, including caste, religion, ethnicity, gender, language, and regional differences. Since Nepal was declared a Federal Republic under the Interim Constitution of 2063, ongoing state restructuring processes have emerged as significant obstacles to development. It is imperative to address these differences effectively to prevent potential future violent conflicts. The nation-building process has given rise to numerous challenges, particularly regarding the assertion of singular identities by different groups. Issues such as state restructuring, power-sharing, boundary delineation, and the quest for singular identity have intensified conflicts due to the diverse demographics encompassing various castes, ethnicities, languages, religions, socio-economic classes, genders, and marginalized communities. Social exclusion and economic disparities further exacerbate tensions and contribute to unrest, underscoring the necessity of managing these challenges effectively to achieve lasting peace and sustainable development.

Objectives of the Research

The primary focus of this study is to uncover the underlying reasons for conflict rooted in the socio-economic framework of society. Nepal contends with numerous internal and external conflicts, but the central issue lies in internal conflicts that exacerbate issues such as hunger, poverty, and developmental stagnation. These conflicts are closely tied to human rights violations, political instability, societal distrust, and rising crime rates. It is imperative to identify strategies for social development, lasting peace, and economic advancement to effectively mitigate and ultimately resolve these conflicts.

Nepal and its citizens are currently engaged in the formulation of a new constitution through a constituent assembly, tasked with restructuring the state while emphasizing the right to self-determination for historically marginalized groups. The constituent assembly is committed to establishing Nepal as an inclusive Federal Democratic Republic. Consequently, research on inclusion agendas and nation-building has become crucial for informing decision-making and supporting civil society advocacy aimed at safeguarding and advancing the rights of excluded groups within the constitution.

Some specific objectives include:

To identifying the fundamental reasons behind conflicts in Nepal and their consequences.

To examine critically the potential challenges arising from emerging issues, cultural dialogues, impacts of globalization, and the transformation of conflicts.

To examine social inequalities and the exclusion experienced by various groups.

To propose recommendations for enhancing societal improvements through effective inclusion strategies.

Significance of the study

The significance of this research lies in its potential to assist Nepalese policymakers in identifying the root causes of conflict and devising strategies for achieving social and economic growth and welfare. By addressing social exclusion, the study aims to combat various societal issues through increased awareness, literacy, and equitable resource distribution. Integrating marginalized and excluded communities into the mainstream of social development is crucial for preventing potential threats such as social unrest, civil conflict, and instability. Essentially, this study proposes a narrative of conflict, transformation, and reconstruction, offering insights into Nepal's evolution since the turbulent Maoist insurgency. It prompts further exploration and discussion on the changes in Nepalese society, politics, economy, and governance that have occurred in the aftermath of these conflicts. It has even displayed how the nation has been built and how complex it has become even to come in the normal condition in the post insurgency and it has its own importance for the conflict-oriented nations for learning and knowing the ideas of the settlement of the ongoing conflicts anywhere in the world.

Limitations of the study

Critical assessments indicate that the process of drafting the constitution in Nepal has been dominated through aristocrats, in spite of the standard inclusion in backward communities, who still lack meaningful participation. Additionally, there is criticism regarding the internal democracy within political parties, as decision-making is heavily centralized around a small group of 12-13 top leaders who wield control over parties, parliament, executive functions, and even influence the judiciary through syndicate systems. This centralized control limits the participation of ordinary parliamentarians and excludes broader public involvement in the Constituent Assembly's decision-making processes.

The limitations of this study are evident as it primarily focuses on the social and economic structures of Nepalese society and their role in conflict. It aims to address the root causes of conflict through socio-economic measures, emphasizing the need to integrate diverse groups into mainstream representation across all sectors. The study also seeks to explore potential positive outcomes stemming from conflicts in Nepal.

Research methodology

This research adopts both a descriptive and analytical approach, drawing on secondary data collected from a variety of sources. These include library books, online resources, and published materials such as newspapers, books, magazines, and archived documents related to topics of inclusion, policy-making, and political representation. Statistical data and historical evidence are obtained from reputable and dependable sources to ensure accuracy and validity. Additionally, the study references authoritative websites and external links to examine established theories and concepts. Moreover, the researcher incorporates contemporary shifts in the prevailing political landscape, engaging in constructive dialogue and critical analysis. Personal insights and perspectives contribute significantly to the study's findings, enhancing the depth and breadth of understanding on the subject matter.

Findings

The Maoist insurgency, launched by the Communist Party of Nepal (Maoist) on February 13, 1996, aimed to topple the Nepalese monarchy and establish a people's republic. This conflict ended with the signing of the Comprehensive Peace Accord on November 21, 2006. Following the accord, the United Nations initiated a mission, UNMIN, to monitor the peace process in Nepal for four years, working towards a sustainable resolution. Under the guidance of Prime Minister Dr. Baburam Bhattarai, efforts were made to permanently address the conflict, including the disbanding of the Maoist militia. The conflict was characterized by severe violence, including murders, massacres, purges, kidnappings, war crimes, and crimes against humanity, resulting in the deaths of over 17,000 individuals, including civilians, insurgents, police, and military personnel. It also led to significant internal displacement, impacting hundreds of thousands of people, particularly in rural areas of Nepal.

According to Madhabi Bhatta, a commissioner cited in Wikipedia, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission has received approximately 63,000 complaints related to these incidents. Nepal endured a decade-long Maoist conflict that commenced in February 1996 under the banner of a people's war. During this period, more than 13,000 lives were lost, and over 200,000 people were displaced, with substantial economic losses incurred. However, the country transitioned into a post-conflict phase following the signing of the Comprehensive Peace Accord (CPA) on November 21, 2006. The government now faces a series of tasks aimed at implementing the CPA, including the crucial step of conducting constituent assembly elections to pave the way for lasting peace.

In this post-conflict phase, it is essential to prioritize and implement activities that address both short-term and long-term needs. Immediate efforts should focus on reconstruction and rehabilitation projects to provide relief to conflict victims and enhance service delivery. Special attention must be given to vulnerable groups such as internally displaced persons and children, ensuring their rights are protected and their needs are met.

Furthermore, there is a critical need for programs promoting social and economic inclusion. These initiatives aim to build capacity within marginalized communities, thereby contributing to the achievement of long-term development goals, including the Millennium Development Goals. This comprehensive approach seeks to consolidate the gains made in achieving peace and stability in Nepal following the turbulent years of conflict (Tiwari; 4). This research has utilized a wide array of essential books, documents, research data, and journals that highlight the socio-economic exclusion and discrimination that contributed to conflict in Nepal. It aims not only to shed light on the resolution of socio-economic conflicts but also to emphasize the necessity of genuine inclusion of diverse groups. While formal political equality might seem to address issues, it can mask the persistent exclusion and oppression within society (Dryzek, 1996, p. 475, as referenced in Lawou, 2007c, p. 58). This perspective highlights the necessity of tackling underlying causes and ensuring broad-based inclusion for effective and lasting conflict resolution. Since the 1990s, there has been a growing belief in the international community that establishing liberal political and economic institutions is key to resolving conflicts (Stokke, 2011, p. 323). Research indicates that there has been a notable increase in representation among elite groups such as Brahmins and Chhetris in the House of Representatives elections of 1994, 1996, and 1999, while representation of hill ethnic groups, Madhesis, and Janjatis has declined. This disparity has fueled discontent among these marginalized groups, leading to violent conflicts in society and highlighting deficiencies in inclusive governance across various sectors (Pyakurel, 2013).

Effective political inclusion necessitates addressing issues related to caste, ethnicity, gender, religion, and language, and meeting the demands for ethnic and regional autonomy. The Maoist insurgency that began in 1996 underscored the failure to adequately involve diverse groups in public governance and decision-making processes.

In recent years, the dynamics of class struggle in Nepal resemble those seen in Europe during the industrial era, where workers faced significant economic disparity and inequality. Women's status was similarly marginalized, reflecting a class structure where the wealthy held elevated social positions while others, particularly women, endured numerous disadvantages compared to men (Perkin, 1971: 13-25). A fundamental challenge in nation-building lies in socio-economic disparities, a problem that has been documented since the population census of 1952/54 (Gurung, 1998). These disparities encompass differences in class, gender, caste, ethnicity, region, and religion, among others, which contribute to societal conflicts. Factors such as poverty, unemployment, illiteracy, distrust, exploitation, unequal distribution of resources, and socio-economic and political disparities further exacerbate these conflicts (Shivakoti, 2070: 300). In recent times, the influence of modernization and democracy has fostered increased awareness among various ethnic groups, civil society organizations, and political parties in Nepal. This has led to a more assertive push towards adopting scientific and secular policies. The traditional idea of homogeneity is now being contested, as there is growing demand for pluralistic rights within society (Azam, 2001: 72). The inherent contradictions within Nepali society are the primary drivers of conflict. The state has consistently neglected to proactively implement policies that accommodate all societal groups through mechanisms outlined in the constitution and other legal frameworks. Furthermore, it has failed to embrace inclusive and empowering policies that adequately address the needs of the diverse communities (Pysku and Adhikari, 2013: 39). Below are listed some of the positive impacts of the Maoist conflict that have resulted in beneficial changes in Nepal.

- The constitution was enacted to protect the rights of the people.
- Lasting peace was achieved.
- Nepal transitioned to a republican system of governance.
- The monarchy was abolished.
- Nepal became a federal democratic republic.
- Secularism was adopted.
- Inclusive representation was introduced to safeguard the rights of marginalized and underprivileged groups.
- A mixed electoral system (combining First-Past-the-Post and Proportional Representation with closed lists) was implemented for Constituent Assembly, federal, provincial, and local elections.
- Nepal was restructured into seven provinces to enhance administrative efficiency nationwide.
- The constitution reflects and upholds the aspirations and will of the people through its provisions.
- Reservation quotas were established across various sectors to ensure inclusivity.
- Various commissions were established to promote the rights and interests of women, indigenous groups (Janajati), Tharu community, Madhesis, and others.
- Numerous economic initiatives were launched to foster national development.

- Extensive efforts were undertaken to eradicate all forms of discrimination.
- Goals were set to achieve Millennium Development Goals and Sustainable Development Goals for comprehensive national development.

After nearly two and a half centuries of social exclusion and a decade-long conflict, Nepal has had an opportunity to address longstanding issues stemming from deliberate exclusionary practices. Centuries of social exclusion have led to significant gaps in understanding the lives, beliefs, and characteristics of various groups. Many misconceptions about inclusivity and the restructuring of the state into a federation based on ethnicity and language have been dispelled since 2009 (Lawoti 2009, 1). Since 2006, addressing the inclusion of historically marginalized groups has become a key priority in political discussions. In the current process of drafting the constitution, marginalized groups are identified as those facing political, economic, and social exclusion, often due to discrimination, geographic isolation, or other forms of deprivation. This category also includes communities that are at risk of extinction or extreme marginalization (Constituent Assembly Secretariat 2010, 13). In Nepal, such marginalized groups encompass women, indigenous communities, the Madhesi people in the southern Terai region, and the Dalits (lower caste) collectively comprising more than two-thirds of the country's population (Lawoti 2007, 9). Moreover, it has become one of the challenges of bringing the marginalized groups in the mainstream of the nation.

As of the time of writing the paper, Nepal had recently conducted elections for a second Constituent Assembly in November 2013. The Nepali Congress (NC) emerged as the top party with 196 seats, followed by the Unified Marxist-Leninist (UML) with 175 seats, while the Unified Communist Party of Nepal (Maoist) (UCPN-M) came in third with only 80 seats. Both the NC and UML increased their seat count compared to the 2008 elections, whereas the UCPN-M saw a significant reduction, losing nearly two-thirds of its seats. The Madhesi Janadhikar Forum (MJF) secured 10 seats, down from 54 in 2008. It has become one of the challenges in addressing the voices of the people both from the reconstruction and development in the different parts of the nation and at the same time it has had the burning issues of the social inclusion from the political representation and reconstruction of the country on time. Election has had its own significance in meeting the voice of suppressed and marginalized groups and all the parties have had their own policies in addressing the suppressed and silenced voices of the people.

Despite their electoral success, the NC and UML have not significantly embraced their roles as agents of change, showing minimal commitment to the inclusion of marginalized groups. However, this research indicates that compared to other parties, the NC and UML are more inclined to foster inclusivity, especially when challenged by more radical left-wing forces. The Maoists, despite their electoral setback, demonstrated a willingness to abide by democratic rules and frameworks, yet they face significant challenges in transforming the Nepali state, particularly in building stronger alliances within the political community. The ability of the MJF to champion its single-issue agenda is constrained, given its significant loss of support and the rise of competing Madhesi-based parties. Although the issues and conflicts discussed in this thesis are particular to Nepal, they mirror the widespread challenges encountered in democratization processes across socially and ethnically diverse nations in the Global South. The study underscores the importance of forging broad alliances within the political community and highlights the political motivations behind strategies of popular mobilization. These findings contribute to understanding why exclusionary policies persist despite calls for inclusive governance, emphasizing the role of mobilization and organizational strategies in shaping political outcomes in Nepal and beyond.

Inclusion and its Challenges for Implementation

The underrepresentation and influence of various socio-cultural groups in Nepal's government positions reveal significant disparities. Research shows that the Chhetri community holds dominant roles across politics, the executive branch, judiciary, parliament, administration, academia, industry, commerce, civil society, local government, education, and leadership (Neupane, 2000). Together with the Newar community, which makes up 36.37% of the population, they controlled over 80% of key leadership roles in government sectors as of 1999. Despite some progress in areas such as media and civil society, traditionally marginalized groups still face substantial exclusion.

Women, including those from the Chhetri community, are notably underrepresented in public positions. Their presence in the House of Representatives has consistently been below 6% in the years 1991, 1994, and 1999, with some cabinets including no women at all. In 1997, women made up only 5% of the official civil service and 4% of the judiciary (Acharya, 2003; FWLD, 2000, 9). The exclusion is particularly severe for Dalits, who have had minimal representation: only one Dalit has been elected to the House of Representatives, and just one served as a cabinet member between 1990 and 2002. Gurung (2002) discusses how severe income inequalities in developing nations can impede the equitable exercise of citizenship rights. The discourse on group-specific rights centers on their potential to address structural inequalities that contribute to social and political exclusion. These rights aim to redress imbalances and meet the specific needs of minority groups within the political system. However, concerns exist that affirmative action, while intended to foster equality, may unintentionally institutionalize divisions and continue exclusion (Jayal, 2013, 16-17). Young (2011, 16-17) argues that failing to recognize group-specific rights can obscure the oppression faced by groups. By focusing on group similarities rather than individual identities, laws and rights may reflect the values of dominant groups, marginalizing minority perspectives. Kymlicka (1995) advocates for group-specific rights in multicultural societies, arguing they are essential for addressing group inequalities, acknowledging historical group rights, and preserving cultural diversity. He suggests three types of rights: self-government rights for minority autonomy, protective rights to safeguard identities and cultures, and representation rights to ensure political presence. While the latter two seek to integrate minority groups into the national framework, self-government rights might challenge the unity of the state, potentially leading to fragmentation.

The paper has identified several challenges in Nepal's democratization process and even the paths of getting them solved. Citizenship policies are largely seen as exclusionary, contributing to issues around state restructuring and the empowerment of various identity groups. The dominance of elite executives poses another obstacle to nation-building efforts. Inter-group mistrust exacerbates controversies and fuels widespread structural violence. The federal division has also strained relations between indigenous peoples, Janajatis, Madhesis, and the four major political parties currently in power.

The lack of substantial representation for excluded and marginalized groups despite their formal presence in constitutional processes underscores ongoing issues. The constitution drafting process has been criticized as elite-led, with a small group of top leaders exerting control over political parties, the constituent assembly (parliament), the executive branch, and influencing the judiciary (SIRF, 2009). Given these challenges, the prospects for achieving social, economic, and political inclusion in Nepal remain uncertain. However, the visionary political leaders and the planners have had to identify such challenges on time and address them as quickly as possible for the betterment of the entire nation. In fact, all the challenges have got their own solutions but what has got is the strong will power and the action to be adopted on time. Any kind of solution comes with the commitment and long-lasting vision to lead and address all the issues raised up to now from

the various levels of the society (Maoist, 1998). In the same way, it has been pointed out that the political commitment and dedication of the issues to be solved by the political leaders for the need of the country has its own way of reconstruction and rebuilding the nation. (Tamang 2011, 306-307). Hence, it has displayed that the political stability and the political leaders' commitment can uncover the obstacles of the nation for the apt and appropriate form of solution of any types of the issues raised from the people and the need of the nation.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The Maoist conflict concluded with the signing of the Comprehensive Peace Accord on November 21, 2006, facilitated by UNMIN (United Nations Mission in Nepal). This conflict ushered in significant changes. The overarching conclusion of this study is that there is a critical need for recovery and reconstruction across all three dimensions - political, economic, and social. Overemphasizing any single dimension, such as solely focusing on political aspects, could potentially undermine the post-conflict situation and hinder the path to enduring peace.

Nepal has progressed in social, economic, and political realms. Previously marginalized, disadvantaged, and underrepresented groups have gained greater inclusion in education, politics, administration, and various other sectors. The introduction of proportional representation in elections has enabled ordinary citizens to participate more actively in political decision-making processes, both in parliament and the cabinet. Institutionalizing democratic norms among citizens is essential for ensuring effective governance within the country. A sense of strong nationalism and patriotism will flourish when Nepal demonstrates equality and fairness across all sectors. To accomplish this goal, specific measures need to be implemented.

- The principles laid out in the constitution should be adhered to consistently, without interruption.
- Citizens should be educated about their rights and responsibilities.
- Social and economic opportunities should be based on principles of equality and fairness.
- Government actions must be accountable and beneficial for the nation.
- A fair and stable government is essential.

The analysis has been concluded that the absence in many inclusive principles stems in various factors. Firstly, the conservative political parties deny the transformation that could risk them in their dominant positions in politics and society at large. When the Maoists re-engaged in parliamentary politics, maintaining unity within the political community became challenging. Beyond mobilizing and advocating change, the Maoists were expected to deliver tangible results for reform. However, they increasingly prioritized specific rights of victimized subgroups over broader socio-economic changes, leading to fragmentation within the political community.

Furthermore, the Maoist party has primarily focused on a single-issue agenda centered around identity-based federalism, which has not effectively promoted broad social and political inclusion at regional and national levels. The findings of this research suggest that the Nepali Congress, along with Tarai Madhes-based parties, is more inclined than the Unified Marxist-Leninist (UML) and other parties to foster greater inclusion, especially when faced with challenges from more radical left-wing forces.

The Maoists themselves experienced a significant loss of seats in the second Constituent Assembly, initially raising doubts about their acceptance of the outcome. However, their acceptance indicates a sincere intention to abide by democratic systems that highlights significant obstacles that the Maoist party must address to become a pivotal force in reshaping the Nepali state, particularly through strengthening its alliances within

the political sphere. The Madhesi Janadhikar Forum's (MJF) focus on a single-issue agenda is constrained by its diminished support and the increasing competition from other Madhesi-oriented parties. Although the issues and conflicts discussed are specific to Nepal, they mirror broader challenges faced in democratization processes within socially and ethnically diverse nations in the Global South.

This study's analytical approach has highlighted the importance of building broad alliances within the political community and understanding the political motivations driving actors' strategies for popular mobilization. It also sheds light on why exclusionary policies persist despite demands for inclusion, not only in Nepal but also in other contexts. One significant factor appears to be the mode of mobilization and organization, which tends to be top-down rather than inclusive from grassroots levels, as observed in many developing countries.

Moreover, the design of the Constituent Assembly favors top leadership, allocating speaking time and committee seats based on votes and party hierarchy, which predominantly benefits high-caste male leaders. Additionally, party pressures often restrict assembly members' freedom of expression, compelling them to align with party positions.

In conclusion, the recommendation for achieving nation-building with enduring peace underscores the need to address the root causes of conflict and enhance local capacities for peace management and conflict resolution. This approach advocates a method that prioritizes basic human needs such as survival, physical well-being, liberty, and identity, fostering a win-win approach. While federalism is crucial for addressing group identities, there must also be room for creativity and a collective sense of solidarity, where one's well-being and suffering are shared concerns. This vision aims to instill a sense of equality, unity, and integrity, enabling Nepal to realize the true essence of nation-building.

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